

The Status Of The Mind In The Holy Quran, Its Synonyms, And Its Functions

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: January 13, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: April 14, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Mind, Islamic Educational Thought, Noble Qur'an</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7826482</p>	<p><i>This study aims to explore the importance and objectives of the mind in Islamic educational thought. The mind is considered one of God's blessings on mankind and is praised in the Noble Qur'an as a means of guidance, truth, and understanding. The study examines the status of the mind and its relationship with its synonyms in the Qur'an and its functions. Using a deductive analytical approach in dealing with the Qur'anic text and an inductive approach in dealing with books of interpretation and other sources and references, the study seeks to answer three main questions: 1) How is the mind defined in the light of Islamic educational thought? 2) What is the relationship between the mind and its synonyms? 3) What are the functions of the mind? The findings reveal that the mind is an innate force within humans that can grow and expand with proper care and attention, leading to greater awareness, understanding, and judgment in matters. The study highlights the importance of nurturing the mind and preventing any hindrances that may impede its development. Overall, the study provides valuable insights into the significance of the mind in Islamic educational thought and its potential for guiding individuals towards truth and enlightenment.</i></p>

Introduction

The role of the mind in Islamic educational thought has been a topic of great interest for scholars throughout history. The mind is considered a vital aspect of the human being, a means of guidance and enlightenment, and a source of knowledge and understanding. In Islamic tradition, the mind is praised as a means of achieving a higher level of consciousness and spiritual awareness, and as a means of understanding the mysteries of creation.

The Noble Qur'an emphasizes the importance of the mind and its synonyms in numerous verses, and it describes the functions of the mind, which include contemplation, reflection, and reasoning. The Qur'an also highlights the relationship between the mind and the heart, and it stresses the importance of using both to achieve a balanced and harmonious existence.

Despite the significant attention given to the mind in Islamic thought, there is still much to be explored and understood about its role and functions. This study aims to clarify the status of the mind and its relationship with its synonyms in the Qur'an and its functions, as well as the importance of nurturing and developing the mind in Islamic education.

The study is guided by three research questions: first, how is the mind defined in the light of Islamic educational thought? Second, what is the relationship between the mind and its synonyms in the Qur'an? And finally, what are the functions of the mind in Islamic educational thought? In answering these questions, the study draws on the deductive analytical approach in dealing with the Qur'anic text and the inductive approach in dealing with books of interpretation and other sources and references.

The findings of the study have important implications for Islamic education and the development of the human mind. The study provides insights into the importance of nurturing the mind and preventing any hindrances that may impede its development. It also highlights the role of the mind in achieving spiritual growth and enlightenment, and the need to use it in conjunction with the heart to achieve a balanced and harmonious existence.

Overall, this study contributes to the understanding of the role of the mind in Islamic educational thought and provides valuable insights into the potential for its development and growth.

The importance and objectives of the study

God created man, provided him with faculties, and endowed him with abilities in order to perform the function of succession on the earth, and the mind is one of God's blessings on man, distinguished him by it over the rest of his creation, and made it the focus of assignment and the basis for honoring, and achieving the goal for which God created man.

The Noble Qur'an drew attention to the importance of the mind, praised the people of intellect who are guided to God Almighty, and clarified the limits of the mind and its position on the unseen, and he referred to the functions of the mind, which are mental operations that it performs as a way to guidance, truth and guidance, and the revelation of the signs of God in souls and horizons.

The Noble Qur'an has taken synonyms with the mind to develop thought, and to stimulate the mind so that it moves and wanders in the vast universe, witnesses it, looks, discovers, invents and creates, and performs multiple functions of contemplation, remembrance, understanding, knowledge, contemplation, jurisprudence, consideration of matters, their vision, and their consequences.

The study aims to clarify the status of the mind and the relationship with its synonyms in the Qur'an and its functions, as it is an innate force in the human being that grows and grows and magnifies his giving and expands his role. If you raise him well, guide him and take care of him, and prevents everything that prevents his implementation and activation. Let us touch its effects in awareness, understanding, comprehension, judgment on matters, rational and intelligent identification in situations, in the quality of thinking, and even in proper behavior, behavior and practical practices, and consideration of its consequences, and if neglected and not taken care of, it gradually tells and loses many of its abilities.

In achieving the objectives of the study, the researcher relied on the deductive analytical approach in dealing with the Qur'anic text, and on the inductive approach in dealing with books of interpretation and other sources and references to clarify the status of the mind, its synonyms and functions in light of the Qur'anic texts by answering the following questions:

- The first question: Defining the mind in the light of Islamic educational thought.
- The second question: the relationship between the mind and its synonyms.
- The third question: the functions of the mind

The study plan came in an introduction, three sections and a conclusion.

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The first topic: the mind in Islamic education

The first requirement: Defining the mind

1. Mind in language:
 - Al-Fayrouzabadi said: "Mind: is the opposite of foolishness, like the intelligible, and the plural is minds: And the mind of a thing means understanding it."
 - Al-Ragheb said: "The mind is said of the power that is prepared to accept knowledge, and it is said of the knowledge that a person benefits from that power of the mind."
2. Mind in terms:
 - Al-Muhasabi said: "The mind is an instinct that God Almighty has placed in most of His creation that people have not seen, and the mind is a light in the heart like the sight is a light in the eye."
 - Ibn al-Jawzia said: "Know that the investigation into this is that this name, I mean the mind, applies jointly to four meanings.

One of them: the description by which man separates from the beasts, and he is the one who is prepared to accept the theoretical sciences and the management of the hidden intellectual industries, and it is what was intended by those who said instinct, it is as if a light is cast into the heart, preparing it to perceive things.

The second: what has been placed in the nature of knowledge of the permissibility of rewards, and the impossibility of the impossible.

The third: sciences that are drawn from experiences called the mind.

The fourth: That the ultimate power of instinct is until it suppresses the desire that calls for immediate pleasure.

The second requirement: Islam and the mind

God, Glory be to Him, created man in a perfect manner, distinguished him, honored him, and raised him above all other creatures with his mental faculty, with which he made him the basis for the duties of the baptism of this world. God Almighty said: (We have certainly created man in the best of stature) And the Almighty said: (And indeed We have honoured the Children of Adam, and We have carried them on land and sea) Just as man was created from the beginning for a specific purpose, which is the worship of God Almighty. And the Almighty said: (And I (Allah) created not the jinns and humans except they should worship Me (Alone).) God made him qualified for this and made him known to himself from the beginning, and did not leave him for his thought to know his Lord through reflection and contemplation; The heavenly laws were revealed from the Lord of the worlds, God Almighty said: (And whoever seeks a religion other than Islam, it will never be accepted of him, and in the Hereafter he will be one of the losers.) Thus, man was able to innovate, present, develop his ways of life and protect it from the dangers surrounding him, and this goes back to what God has honored and favored man with, that he has endowed him with the ability to learn and knowledge. God Almighty said: ((3) Recite, and your Lord is the most Generous -Who taught by the pen- Taught man that which he knew not). Man is born in this world with innate and mental preparations. Instinctive instincts do not need to be taught, as they operate automatically directed to the worship of God Almighty. God Almighty said: **(the fitrah of Allah upon which He has created [all] people. No change should there be in the creation of Allah That is the correct religion, but most of the people do not know)** And as the Messenger of God, Muhammad, peace be upon him, said: **“Every child is born according to the fitrah, then his parents make him a Jew or a Christian.**

The instinct may be forgotten or deviated as a result of the environment that is not surrounding the individual, and a mercy from God Almighty and His kindness to man, He sent messengers and prophets and sealed them with the Messenger Muhammad, peace be upon him, to remind people of the Creator, the Mighty and Sublime, and to guide them towards the right path. God Almighty said: **(So remind, [O Muhammad]; you are only a reminder)** As for the faculty of reason, by which God Almighty distinguished man from all other creatures because of its characteristics that enable man to carry out the task of succession on earth, the Almighty said: **(And [remember] when your Lord said to the angels, “I am going to appoint a vicegerent on earth.” They said, “Will You appoint on it someone who will spread corruption therein and shed blood, while we glorify You with Your praises and proclaim Your holiness?” He said, “I know that which you do not know, And He taught Adam all the names (of everything), then He showed them to the angels and said, “Tell Me the names of these if you are truthful.”, They said, “Exalted are You; we have no knowledge except what You have taught us. Indeed, it is You who is the Knowing, the Wise.”, He said, “O Adam, inform them of their names.” And when he had informed them of their names, He said, “Did I not tell you that I know the unseen [aspects] of the heavens and the earth? And I know what you reveal and what you have concealed)**, and perhaps this indicates the reality of the message that a person should aspire to in his life, which is to carry out the task of succession, also, the mental ability to acquire knowledge is one of the main pillars for achieving these tasks; The mind is an existing quality in man, and it is the tool for perceiving, understanding, looking at, receiving, discerning and balancing. It is the human means to fulfill the responsibility of existence and action in the world of martyrdom and life. Al-Harith Al-Muhasabi said: “Everything has an essence, and the essence of man is the mind.” Also, the mind is one of the human tools for contemplating the kingdom of heaven and earth, as we find the verses of the Noble Qur’an working to move the mind for consideration, insight and consideration, God Almighty said: (And on the earth are signs for the certain [in faith], and also in your own selves. Will you not then see?) .As the wise Qur’an clarifies the mental faculty’s responsibility for human behavior and actions, the Almighty said: (And follow not (O man i.e., say not, or do not or witness not, etc.) that of which you have no knowledge (e.g. one’s saying: “I have seen,” while in fact he has not seen, or “I have heard,” while he has not heard). Verily! The hearing, and the sight, and the heart, of each of those you will be questioned (by Allah).) Islamic education develops the mind on sound thinking, humility, acceptance of truth, scientific honesty, pursuit of truth without obsession, and benefiting from what is known, not being satisfied with theoretical knowledge, but rather a practical application.

Islamic education develops the mind on sound thinking, humility, acceptance of truth, scientific honesty, pursuit of truth without obsession, and benefiting from what is known, not being satisfied with theoretical knowledge, but rather a practical application. Also, it has been proven that Islamic education,

although it does not explicitly stipulate the development of the mind, but its visionary goal includes mental light as well as physical development, it directs this mental aspect of education towards accuracy in thinking, honesty, and practical application, and towards working to know God in his traces, verses and creatures towards insight and guidance, and keeping away from whims and blind imitation, and towards seeking evidence, certain knowledge, and distance from conjecture.

The wise Qur'anic verses direct man to employ his mental capacity in contemplation, and reflection, and that man needs to learn to acquire knowledge in order to develop his mental abilities and preparations that God has endowed him with, also, the exemplary behavior commanded by Islam is the one that emanates from the foundations laid by the Islamic Sharia in order to find the greatest degree of harmony and consistency between man and his innate desires in this life and in accordance with correct logic and thinking; The Holy Qur'an calls for educating the mind and providing it with various educational means that enable it to think sound and mature, the one who contemplates the verses of the wise Qur'an which call for the arbitration of the mind and push it to realize the meanings of truth, goodness and beauty to carry out the tasks that God has assigned him to do, and if the intellect deviates from correctness and pursues desires in contravention of God's law; Corruption spread and chaos prevailed, the Book of God Almighty also mourns for those who do not use their minds, so it resembles them to wild beasts. Almighty said: **(Indeed the worst of all the creatures with Allah are the deaf and dumb – those who cannot heed)**. The human mind, with the capabilities that God has endowed with it, will enable it to comprehend the laws of existence, learn them, recognize their meanings and dimensions, and affect them and be affected by them, it is also surrounded by God's care and care within the guidelines of the Book of God and the Sunnah of His Prophet Muhammad ﷺ since the beginning of creation and over time until he inherits the earth and those on it. Sahib Alzilal said: "Islam is the religion of the mind...yes...in the sense that it addresses the mind with its issues and decisions, and does not defeat it with a materialistic breakthrough that has no room except by submission, and it addresses the mind in the sense that it corrects its approach to consideration and invites it to reflect on the signs of guidance and the revelations of faith in souls and horizons; To remove from the instinct the pile of elusiveness, habit, and dullness, and the pile of lusts that mislead the mind and instinct, and address the mind in the sense that it is entrusted with understanding the meanings of the texts that carry its decisions, and does not force him to believe in what he does not understand and does not comprehend...If he reaches the stage of realizing the meanings and understanding the decisions, he has no choice but to accept them, then he is a believer, or not to accept them, then he is an infidel...And it is not a ruling on its validity or invalidity, and it is not authorized to accept or reject it, as those who wish to make of this mind a deity say what is accepted from the correct religious decisions. He refuses from it what he rejects, deceives from it what he wills, and leaves from it what he wills.

Abu Ashour said: "Insight is the plural of insight, and it is by which the truth becomes clear, It was presented when the Almighty said: **(Verily, proofs have come to you from your Lord, so whosoever sees, will do so for (the good of) his ownself, and whosoever blinds himself, will do so to his own harm, and I (Muhammad SAW) am not a watcher over you)** This is a disclaimer regarding the Qur'an and that it is better than the verses they ask, because it combines the evidence of the Messenger's sincerity by means of the inimitability and its emanating from the illiterate, and between guidance, education, guidance, and permanence for the ages. Rather the plural of "insights" because in the Qur'an there are types of guidance according to the areas to which it is guided. From enlightening the mind in reforming belief, advancing understanding in religion, laying down laws for dealings and cohabitation among people, indicating the ways of success and salvation in this world, and warning against the abyss of loss.

The third requirement: Reason in the Qur'an:

Islam has paid great attention to the mind, as by it man understands and reason, and knowledge, will and ability follow him. One of the manifestations of the Qur'an's interest in the mind and its supplies and dependencies is that the words "their minds, they reason, we reason, he rationalizes them" are mentioned in forty-nine places in the Holy Book. The word "al-bab" appears in sixteen places. Al-lbab is the plural of the core, which is the mind. Also, the word "Ouli al-Nuha" is mentioned in the Holy Qur'an, meaning the people of intellects. As for the places that talk about the functions of the mind, such as thinking, remembering, contemplating, considering matters and rationality, the verses in that are many. Almighty says: (Thus Allah makes clear the Ayat (these Verses or your religious symbols and signs, etc.) to you that you may understand) (Verily, We have sent it down as an Arabic Qur'an in order that you may understand) (and adhere to the Commandments of Allah, O you of (sound) understanding) (Say, "Is the blind equivalent to the seeing? Then will you not give thought?) (And among His Signs is this, that He created for you wives from among yourselves, that you may find repose in them, and He has put between your affection and mercy. Verily, in that are indeed signs for a people who reflect.) (And they will say, "If only we had been listening or reasoning, we would not be among the companions of the Blaze).

The fourth requirement: the reality of the mind:

The mind in man is one of the signs of God Almighty. Al-Mahsiri said: "If a person contemplates, he would see how many verses in his mouth fill the soul with astonishment and submission. And the research into the nature of the mind and its essence so that there is no point behind it, except that it is agreed that it is a means of understanding, discernment and judgment, so God made it the subject of the assignment. With mind, God chose man above all other creatures, raised his level, empowered him on the earth and appointed him as his successor, and made him capable of understanding the aspects of the universe with his intellect. Ibn Khaldun said: "And in the gradual formation of the human being who has thought and vision, it rises to him from the realm of power in which sense and perception are combined. The mind is the tool of thinking, and man writes knowledge through it, by analysis, synthesis, measurement, conclusion, and linkage. The Qur'an is full of examples that urge Muslims to use their minds and thinking in choosing, discriminating, and making comparisons. Rather, it also enables Muslims to exercise reason in matters that are not mentioned in an explicit religious text. And the reference in the Noble Qur'an to mental abilities if they came in the form of a verb and not a noun, and as one of the functions of the heart and one of its actions that take place inside the human being before it turns into a living exercise on his external organs. Almighty said: (So have they not traveled through the earth and have hearts by which to reason). The mind, then; A reference to a function and not to an existing thing that we desire, like the functions of understanding, eating and drinking. The mind is a management of thinking. The Sahib Alzilali said: The role of this mind is to receive from the message, and its function is to understand what it receives from the Messenger, and the mission of the Messenger is to inform, clarify, and criticize the human instinct from what they see from the rubble and it alerts the human mind to reflect on the evidence of guidance and the revelations of faith in the souls and horizons, and draws for it the correct approach to receiving, and the correct approach to looking, and to establish for it the basis on which the practical life is based, leading to the good of this world and the hereafter. It is not the role of the mind to be a judge of religion and its decisions in terms of validity and invalidity, acceptance or rejection, after it has been confirmed that they are correct from God and after understanding their intended meaning (i.e. the linguistic and idiomatic implications of the text), even if he were to accept it or reject it after realizing its meaning; Because it is he who does not agree with this meaning or does not want to respond to it! What deserves punishment from God for disbelief after the clarification... So he is obligated to accept the decisions of the religion when they reach the right path, and when his mind understands what is meant by it and what is meant by it... This message addresses the mind... in the sense that it awakens it, directs it, and establishes the correct approach to it... Not in the sense that he is the one who judges their validity and invalidity, their acceptance or rejection. And when the text was established, it was the ruling, and the human mind had to accept it, obey it, and implement it, whether its connotation was familiar or alien to it.

Imam Al-Ghazali explained the reality of the mind and the people's disparity in it: "I know that people differed in terms of the definition and reality of the mind, and others were astonished that this name was absolute with four meanings, the name of the eye, for example, is given to several meanings, and what is going on in this stream, it should not be required for all its sections to have one limit, but to single out each section by revealing it:

The first is the description with which man separates from other animals, and it is by which he prepares to accept theoretical sciences and manage hidden intellectual industries, and this is what Al-Harith bin Asad Al-Muhasabi wanted, when he said: In the limit of the mind: it is an instinct with which the comprehension of theoretical sciences is prepared, as if it is a light cast into the heart with which it prepares to perceive things, he did not do justice to those who denied this and referred the intellect to merely the necessary sciences, for the one who is unaware of the sciences and the one who sleeps is called sane, given the presence of this instinct in them with the loss of sciences, and just as life is an instinct by which the body prepares for voluntary movements and sensory perceptions, likewise, the mind is an instinct by which some animals are prepared for theoretical sciences, even if it is permissible to equate a human with a donkey in terms of instinct and sensory perceptions.

He said: There is no difference between them except that God Almighty, by virtue of the conduct of habit, creates knowledge in man and does not create it in donkeys and beasts. It is permissible to equate the donkey and the inanimate in life, and it is said: There is no difference except that God, the Mighty and Sublime, creates in the donkey specific movements by virtue of the practice of habit, for if a donkey is estimated to be inanimate and dead, it must be said that every movement is seen from it because God Almighty is able to create it in it in the order that is seen. And as it must be said, his separation from inanimateness in movements was only through an instinct that was specific to it and expressed in life, this is how the animal departed from man in perceiving the theoretical sciences with an instinct expressed by the mind. It is like the mirror that does not separate from other bodies in the narration of images and colors, an attribute that is specific to it, which is the glaze, likewise, the eye separates from the forehead in characteristics and bodies that are prepared for vision, as the relation of this instinct to the sciences is like the relation of the eye to vision, and the relation of the Qur'an and Sharia to this instinct in its context to the exposure of sciences to it is like the relation of the sun's light to the sight, and this is how this instinct should be understood.

The second: It is the sciences that come into existence in the self of the distinguished child by the permissibility of rewards and the impossibility of the impossible, such as the knowledge that two are more than one and that one person cannot be in two places at the same time, it is what some of the theologians meant when he said in the limit of the mind: It is some of the necessary sciences, such as the knowledge of the permissibility of the permissible and the impossibility of the impossible, and it is also true in itself; Because these sciences exist and call them the apparent mind, rather, it is corrupt that you deny that instinct and say: There is no existence except for these sciences.

The third: sciences that are benefited from experiences in the course of conditions, for those who have been savvy by experiences and refined by sects are said to be sane usually, whoever does not have this characteristic and is said to be stupid and ignorant, then this is another type of science, which is called intellect.

Fourth: That the strength of that instinct ends until he knows the consequences of these matters and suppresses the desire that calls for immediate pleasure and subdues it, if this force occurs, the owner is called sane, in that his stubbornness and reluctance are in accordance with what is required by the consideration of the consequences by virtue of immediate desire. This is also one of the characteristics of man that distinguishes him from other animals.

As for people's differences in the mind, he said: "The correct truth about it is that it is said that disparity refers to the four categories, except for the second category: It is the necessary knowledge of the permissibility of the prizes and the impossibility of the impossible.

For whoever knows that two are more than one, he also knows that it is impossible for a body to be in two places, and for a single thing to be ancient and contingent, the same applies to other analogues and everything that is comprehended by an undoubted realization. As for the three sections, the variance deals with them. As for the fourth section: It is the seizure of power over the suppression of desires, so it is not hidden from people's disparity in it, rather it is not hidden from the disparity in the conditions of one person in him, and this disparity is sometimes due to the disparity of desire, a wise person may be able to leave some desires and not others, but it is not limited to him. A young man may be unable to leave fornication, and if he grows up and his mind is fully developed, the desire for hypocrisy and leadership grows stronger with arrogance, not weakness, that is why the doctor is able to avoid some harmful foods and give precedence to what is equal in the mind to that, if he is not a doctor, even if he believes in general that it is harmful, but if the physician's knowledge was complete, his fear would be greater, so fear would be a soldier for the mind and a tool for it to suppress and break desires, likewise, the scholar will be more capable of forsaking sins than the ignorant because of the power of his knowledge of the harm of disobedience, and by it I mean the real world without the lords of the robbers and delirium holders, if the discrepancy is from the side of desire, it is not due to the discrepancy of the intellect, and if it is from the aspect of knowledge, then we have called this kind of knowledge intellect as well. If the discrepancy is from the side of desire, it is not due to the discrepancy of the intellect, and if it is from the aspect of knowledge, then we have called this kind of knowledge intellect as well, it strengthens the mind, so the discrepancy is in what the name refers to, and it may be just the discrepancy in the instinct of the mind, for if it is strengthened, its suppression of lust will inevitably be more severe. As for the third category: It is the science of experiences, so people's variation in them is not denied, as they vary in the frequency of injury and speed of perception, and the cause is either a discrepancy in instinct or a discrepancy in practice.

The fifth requirement: The mind's limits:

The Holy Qur'an considered human nature and its limitations, so it addressed it in a discourse that human minds understand, and did not reveal to us what our minds cannot bear, "A general characteristic of the Islamic faith, which deals with the universal realities, and defines them within the limits of what humans need and improve their conditions in cohabitation, and what their minds understand, since God, the Mighty and Sublime, did not inform us of all the unseen.

Sahib Alzilal commented on the limitations of the mind and its being a tool that has a certain amount of energy in the nature of creation and formation, and the Qur'an did not carry it beyond its capacity. Sayed said: likewise, God will never let people know the unseen, as they are not prepared by the nature that God created them with to see the unseen. And their human apparatus, which God has given them, is not designed on the basis of receiving this unseen except in proportion, and it is thus wisely designed, designed to perform the function of the caliphate on earth, and it does not need to see the unseen, and if the human apparatus is opened to the unseen, this apparatus will be destroyed; Not because he is prepared to receive him except to the extent that his soul connects with his Creator, and his being connects with the entity of this universe. Also, it does not need to see the unseen, and if the human apparatus is opened to the unseen, this apparatus will be destroyed; Not because he is prepared to receive him except to the extent that his soul connects with his Creator, and his being connects with the entity of this universe.

Moreover, he says, may God have mercy on him, that when the Qur'an talks about the supernatural, it links them to the destiny of God alone, and this would make the minds accept "As for how the supernatural happened, just as every supernatural happens! Just as the first supernatural life occurred, the supernatural that we forget it happened and we don't know how it happened! And we also do not know how it came except that it

came from God in the way that God wanted... Thus, Darwin, the greatest scientist of life, continues to descend in his theory of life step by step, and he goes deep into its depths, bottom to bottom until he returns it to the first cell... Then he stops there, as he is ignorant of the source of life in this first cell as if he does not want to accept what human perception should accept, So he says: "The interpretation of life's affairs with the presence of the Creator is tantamount to introducing a supernatural element into a purely mechanical situation!"...Any mechanical condition! Mechanism is the farthest thing from this matter, which requires the perception to search for a source for this secret that is based on sights and insights!

The sixth requirement: the position of the mind on the unseen:

The mind is the faculty that man thinks of, with which God has honored him above all other creatures, and it is the creative energy, through which man has achieved his civilization and advancement on this earth, and with this, the human mind is in need of rationalization, care, correction, refinement, and defining its path and the scope of its thinking, and the areas of using the mind in order for the mind to produce the good and true happiness that God Almighty wants. Islam alone plays the unique role in defining all of this and then coordinates between the mind and other energies in man, when it addresses this human being and directs its energies, as he considers them to be coordinated energies that serve each other to achieve one goal, despite the different fields of each of these energies.

So the soul, mind and body are linked to each other, although each has its own field, If a person walks with his mind, planning his way of life for him and drawing his depiction of the universe and life and in every matter and thing, he will undoubtedly lose the way as the material civilization and ancient and modern philosophies have gone astray. It did not gain from the arbitration of reason in everything except misery, unhappiness and turmoil, and this error is not evidenced by the reality of civilization today, which gave the mind absolute freedom and lifted it from accountability and reckoning. In Islam, we find the strong connection between the mind and the soul. In fact, Islam makes the soul dominating the mind and directing it in many matters, the mind has nothing to do with the unseen, rather its task is to submit to everything that comes to it from that.

He gives man his share of these unseen to the extent that satisfies his inclination for the unknown, but he entrusts the matter to the soul, for it is capable of that, provided with the means of access, as for the intellect, its means to God and to the knowledge of the truth is to contemplate the outward appearance of the senses and is perceived by the intellect, and then Islam defines its scope with this scope. And he does not let him drown in the labyrinth into which philosophy and theology were immersed before, so that they did not reach anything real worthy of the effort that was put into them. If the mirror of human thought has not darkened, and the lights that are reflected on it have not been scattered.

Sahib Alzilal and Ibn Ashour spoke about the limits of the mind and its standing in the unseen with submission and faith because it is beyond the power of the mind alone. Sayyid said: "As for those who do not believe in this Qur'an and arbitrarily deny these concepts just because knowledge has not reached any of them, they are really funny! Since science does not know the secrets of the existents that appear in its hands, which it uses in its experiments, and this does not negate its existence, of course! In addition to the fact that many of the true scholars have taken to believing in the unknown on the path of the religious, or at least they do not deny what they do not know! Because by experience they found themselves by the method of knowledge itself. The universe around us is full of secrets, brimming with spirits, and gathering strength, and this surah of the Qur'an, like others, gives us aspects of the truths in this existence, which helped to build a true and correct conception of existence and the forces, souls and lives in it that circulate around us and interact with our lives and ourselves. This conception is what distinguishes the Muslim and stands in the middle between illusion and superstition, and between pretense and arrogance, and its source is the Qur'an and the Sunnah, and to them, the Muslim is judged by every other conception, every saying, and every interpretation, and that there is a certain scope for the human mind to explore the horizons of the unknown... Islam pushes it to do so... But behind this particular field there is what this mind is not capable of going to, because there is no need for it to go there, and what it has no need for in the caliphate of the earth, there is no room for it, and there is no wisdom in helping it to it, because it is not of his business and does not fall within the limits of his competence.

Predestination is necessary for him to know his position in the universe by analogy with what is around him and those around him, and God Almighty has ensured his clarification to him, because it is greater than his energy, and by the extent that enters into his energy, and from him this unseen is specific to angels, demons, spirit, origin and destiny... As for those who were guided by God's guidance, they stood in these matters at the destiny that God revealed to them in His books and on the tongue of His Messengers, and they benefited from it by feeling the greatness of the Creator. Awareness of man's position on earth from these worlds and spirits, and they occupied their mental energy with discovery and knowledge prepared for the mind within the boundaries of this earth and the bodies around it to the extent possible for them.

They took advantage of what they learned in work, production, and construction of this land and the establishment of the caliphate on it, on guidance from God, heading towards Him, rising to what calls them to rise. As for those who were not guided by the guidance of God, they were divided into two major groups: a

group that continued to strive with its limited minds for an unlimited realization from God Almighty, and true knowledge hidden through other than the revealed books, and among them were philosophers who tried to explain this existence and its connections, but they kept stumbling like children who climb a high mountain with no goal to reach its summit, or they are trying to solve the mystery of existence while they have not yet mastered the alphabet! And they had funny conceptions while they were great philosophers, which are really funny when a person combines them with the clear, straight, and beautiful conception that the Qur'an creates. Funny with its stumbles, ridiculous with its paradoxes, ridiculous with its pervasiveness, and ridiculous with its dwarfing in comparison to the greatness of existence by which they explain it... I do not exclude from this the great Greek philosophers, nor the Muslim philosophers who imitated them in the way of thinking, nor the philosophers of the modern era! That is when their perception is compared to the Islamic conception of existence, as this is a division. As for the other group, it despaired of the usefulness of this trend of knowledge. So, she changed her mind to limiting herself and her effort to experimental and applied science, ignoring the unknown. Which there is no way to it, and is not guided by God's guidance, because you cannot realize God! This group was at its peak during the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries, but since the beginning of this century it began to wake up from the all-encompassing scientific arrogance, to escaping matter from its hands and transforming it into radiation of unknown origin and almost unknown law! Islam has remained steadfast on the rock of certainty, granting people from the unknown the destiny in which they are good, providing their mental energy to work in the caliphate of the earth, and preparing for their minds the field in which they work in security. And guide them to that which is better in the unknown and the unknown!

Sahib Alzilal also said: "There are many other matters about which knowledge disputes, either because it did not collect enough observations from them to acknowledge them, or because he did not find a way to interfere with his experiences, these prophetic dreams, and Freud, who tries to deny every spiritual force, could not deny its existence, how do I see a vision of an unknown future, then if this prophecy is actually true after a while? And these hidden feelings that have no name yet, how do I feel that something is going to happen in a little while or that someone is coming in a little while, and then it happens somehow! Indeed, it is arrogance for a person to simply stand to negate such unknown forces in the human being, just because science has not yet found a way to test these forces. The meaning of this is not the acceptance of every supernatural, and the pursuit of every myth... Rather, it is the safest and most prudent for the human mind to take a flexible stance in front of these unknowns... It is never denied or proven at all, he is able, by his means available to him after the ascent of these means, to realize what he is unable to realize now, magic is one of these matters, and the devils teach people such matters, and it may be one of its forms: the ability to suggest and influence, either in the senses and thoughts, or in things and bodies... If the magic that the Qur'an mentioned was caused by Pharaoh's magicians, it was just a fantasy that has no reality. In the words of God Almighty: **He said, "Rather, you throw." And suddenly their ropes and staffs seemed to him from their magic that they were moving (like snakes)**) There is no objection to such influence being a means of differentiating between a man and his wife and between a friend and a friend, since emotions arise from influences, even if the means and effects, and the causes, they do not all happen except by God's permission, as we have mentioned before. Ibn Ashour said when interpreting the verse: **(Say, "I hold not for myself [the power of] benefit or harm, except what Allāh has willed. And if I knew the unseen, I could have acquired much wealth, and no harm would have touched me. I am not except a warner and a bringer of good tidings to a people who believe.)**

The sentence is a preliminary resumed, with the intention of its resumption, to pay attention to its content, so that the hearing will be directed to it. Therefore, the order was repeated by saying it twice. In the words of God Almighty: **(say: Its knowledge is only with Allah), (Say, "Its knowledge is only with my Lord.)** To pay attention to the independence of the saying, and not to be included in the sentence of the spoken saying before it, this was summed up by saying, by informing about the condition of the Messenger, peace and blessings be upon him, towards knowledge of the unseen in order to remove from the minds of the polytheists the illusion that knowing the unseen is associated with the attribute of prophethood. Announcing to the polytheists a commitment that he does not know the unseen and that this does not defy his prophethood until they despair of his being updated with this, and informing Muslims of the distinction between what the prophethood requires and what does not require it, therefore, he denied himself knowing his unseen conditions, in addition to knowing the unseen conditions of others, except as God willed.

The second topic: the relationship between the mind and its synonyms

The first requirement: The heart.

The mind gained the highest importance when it was called the heart, and the word "the heart" has been mentioned in the Book of God, singly and collectively; As for the term "mind" it did not appear in the singular case, and this indicates that there is nothing in the human body that embodies the same name as "mind", while there is a soul called the heart, which is that coniferous flesh located in the chest, Ibn Faris said: "Qalb: Qaf, Lam and Ba'a are two authentic origins, one of which indicates the pure and honorable thing. And

the other is about reversing something from one side to another. The first is the heart: the heart of man and others, named after it because it is the most sincere and sublime thing in it.

The first meaning of the heart is: the coniferous flesh that pumps blood and its flow in the veins, and when it stops, life stops, and there is no clear relationship for this heart with the emotions, thoughts and beliefs related to the second meaning of the heart. This heart is shared by dead and living people, even animals have hearts. As for the second meaning of the heart, Imam Al-Ghazali explained it by saying: "It is a divine gentleness that has an attachment to this bodily heart, and that kindness is the reality of man and he is the perceptive, knowledgeable, and knowledgeable of man, and he is the addressee, the punisher, the reproach, and the demands, and it has a relationship to the physical heart, and the minds of most people have been puzzled in realizing the face of its relationship, then Imam Al-Ghazali says: "Where the word heart is mentioned in the Qur'an and Sunnah, what is meant by it is the meaning that is understood by man and knows the reality of things, and he may be called the heart in the chest, because there is a special relationship between that kindness and the body of the heart, even if it is related to the rest of the body and is informed by it, but it is attached to it through the heart, so its first attachment to the heart is as if it were its place, her kingdom, and her world. So the heart, if it is used in the Qur'an and the Sunnah, comes sometimes in the sense of the vessels of knowledge, i.e. what contains understanding and memorization, which is the mind, and sometimes in the sense of the soul, i.e. what is in it of human life, and sometimes it means carrying understanding and memorization, i.e. the brain that is in the human head, or it may be mentioned and meant the whole of the human being by way of applying the part to the whole, so the word "heart" is one of the common words in its meanings, and the sum of those meanings is "the mind." As for the engorged heart that has a tangible essence, it is something else.

An example of the inclusion of the heart in the Holy Qur'an in the sense of the mind is the Almighty's saying: (Indeed in that is a reminder for whoever has a heart or who listens while he is present [in mind]) with the meaning of the mind and understanding. And the heart here, as Ibn Abbas said, means the mind. Al-Farra said: And this is permissible in Arabic for you to say: You have a heart, your heart is not with you, meaning your mind is not with you. Imam Al-Razi draws attention to the precise meanings of this verse, and says in its meaning: "In the aforementioned verses, beginning with the Almighty's verse: (Qâf. [These letters (Qâf, etc.) are one of the miracles of the Qur'ân, and none but Allâh (Alone) knows their meanings]. By the Glorious Qur'ân, But they wonder that there has come to them a warner from among themselves, and the disbelievers say, "This is an amazing thing.) and with regard to what he mentioned, he repels their astonishment, and his statement that he is a true warner and that the resurrection is a reality, and his temptation and intimidation with reward and punishment, sooner and later, until he completes the speech with the words of God Almighty: (Indeed in that is a reminder for whoever has a heart or who listens while he is present [in mind].) Since their ears, tongues and eyes are not useful to what is asked of them, so is he who does not remember as if he has no heart. As for the saying of God Almighty: (Indeed in that is a reminder for whoever has a heart or who listens while he is present [in mind].) Al-Razi said: "The Qur'an contains a remembrance for each one of how he had a heart with the appearance of the matter. If it does not happen to everyone, then for those who listen and support what we have mentioned, the Almighty's saying: (Indeed in that is a reminder for whoever has a heart or who listens while he is present [in mind].) As he did not say or listen, he informs about an extra request. As for reciting the hearing, it means that the remembrance occurs for the one who does not hold back his hearing but rather sends it by transmission. And if he does not intend to hear like the one who hears in the huge sound, then it happens when the ear is just opened, even if he did not intend to hear, and the hidden sound is not heard except by listening and seeking, so we say, the memory takes place for the one who has a heart, how was his heart for her appearance. If it does not happen, then for someone who has an unclogged ear, what was his condition, whether he listened diligently or did not strive to listen to it. An example of the inclusion of the heart in the Noble Qur'an in the sense of the mind is also the saying of God Almighty to censure the hypocrites who do not use their minds in understanding and contemplation: (And whenever a sūrah is revealed, they look at each other, [as if saying], "Does anyone see you?" and then they dismiss themselves. Allâh has dismissed their hearts because they are a people who do not understand)

The second requirement: Al-Fouad:

The mind was used in the word heart, almighty said: (And do not pursue [745] that of which you have no knowledge. Indeed, the hearing, the sight and the heart - about all those [one] will be questioned.) and it came in the plural form in the Almighty's saying: (Then He proportioned him and breathed into him from His [created] soul [1172] and made for you hearing and vision and hearts [i.e., intellect]; little are you grateful.) The Holy Qur'an urges the use of the heart, meaning the mind, in the field of knowledge and taking responsibility, and for this we find the heart associated with hearing and sight in six cases of the Holy Qur'an, this is because the main role in knowledge is the mind, and sensory experience has no value without it, and for this reason the animal heart has no value because it is without jurisprudence and reason, whereas the mind is the one who stands behind these senses and makes their senses real perceptions and knowledge, and transfers them from the instincts and reflections shared by all other animals that are endowed with such senses, transfers it to the circle of perception, and the Noble Qur'an directs the heart and the senses with it so that it does not delve into what it

is not aware of because it bears full responsibility for everything that comes out of it. Almighty said: (And do not pursue [745] that of which you have no knowledge. Indeed, the hearing, the sight, and the heart - about all those [one] will be questioned.) The Noble Qur'an directs man to give thanks for the grace of the mind and the senses with which God has distinguished him over all other creatures.

The third requirement: Alnuha:

Alnuha means the mind that forbids ugly things or that ends with what he commanded, chose, and narrated. Abu Al-Baqa said: "And among the names of the mind is Alnuha: Because of the end of intelligence and knowledge and looking at it, which is the end of what gives the servant of good that leads to the righteousness of this world and the hereafter. God Almighty said: (Then, has it not become clear to them how many generations We destroyed before them as they walk among their dwellings? Indeed, in that are signs for those of intelligence) The Qur'an directs those people with right way of thinking in this verse to take a lesson and a sermon from the destruction that happened to the unjust nations because of their deviation from the approach of God Almighty and their denial of the prophets.

The fourth requirement: the dream:

And the dream, as the willing said, is not in fact the mind, but they interpreted it with it, because it is one of the causes and effects of the mind, the dream is originally self-control and of course the rage of anger. The previous verse directs the mind to control psychological behavior from tyranny and saying about the Messenger of God what is not permissible to attribute to him.

The fifth requirement: the core:

One of the beautiful names given to the mind in the Qur'an is the word "pulp". and in the plural form "albab", and it is the intellect that is pure of impurities, and it is what purifies the mind, so every core is a mind, and not every mind is a pulp. Abu Al-Baqa' said: Among the names of the mind is the core, and it is called that because the human being is a compound of the body and the mind, so the body is like the crust and the mind is like the core. Almighty said: (There was certainly in their stories a lesson for those of understanding. Never was it [i.e., the Qur'an] a narration invented, but a confirmation of what was before it and a detailed explanation of all things and guidance and mercy for a people who believe.) And the people of intellect are the owners of rational, luminous minds and sound senses. Muhammad Ali al-Jozo said after reviewing the verses in which the derivatives of the word pulp and their meanings were mentioned: If the core in the language is the purest of everything, then we can say that in the Qur'an it is the pinnacle of thinking, the source of wisdom and the basis of discernment, and the source of faith, knowledge and certainty. It is, then, a distinguished intellect, and not an ordinary intellect, rather it is the mind of the elite of the people and the elite of thinkers, who are endowed with wisdom. Then he describes the people of intellect as "the owners of intelligent intellects from among the faithful scholars (in the philosophical term, the intellect is the faculty by force, the core is always the faculty by knowledge or it is an attribute)." Let us contemplate some of the attributes that were mentioned in the context of this noble verse about men of understanding, so that we may try to reach them and imitate them, God Almighty said: (Indeed, in the creation of the heavens and the earth and the alternation of the night and the day are signs for those of understanding- (191) Who remember Allāh while standing or sitting or [lying] on their sides and give thought to the creation of the heavens and the earth, [saying], "Our Lord, You did not create this aimlessly; exalted are You [above such a thing]; then protect us from the punishment of the Fire.) The vocabulary synonymous with the mind has enriched the linguistic meanings of the mind, with each one having its own meaning that expresses an aspect of the human mind that the Qur'an wants to draw our attention to, and one of the most important of these aspects is the moral aspect, which is doing good deeds and avoiding evil, because the mind in Islam is the intellect that leads to the realization of good and evil that are mentioned in the Sharia, moreover, this mind transforms perception into action, for the dream expresses the careful and insightful minds that control the behavior of the soul and direct it towards the moderation that Islam commanded, and the core is the butter of the mind and its peak is illuminated by the light of Jerusalem far from the crusts of illusions, and in both dreams and prohibitions, "preventing the mind from ignorance, and mediation and rushing into what is required of it, and this aspect is one of the important aspects that are entrusted to the mind in guiding the human soul to its goodness and righteousness.

The third topic: the functions of the mind

The first requirement: contemplation:

contemplation It is the realization of the mind in a thing, which is the perceptive power of the sciences, and contemplation is the flow of that power according to the insight of the mind, this is specific to humans, not animals, and some writers said that thought is inverted from rubbing, but the thought is used in it is the rubbing and research of things in order to reach and contemplation as well as the request for previous knowledge by

acquiring new knowledge so every thinker is remembered, but not every thinker is contemplative, and this is because remembrance is just prior knowledge to transfer from it to another knowledge. The benefit of remembrance is to bring knowledge to the focal point of perception so that it becomes firmly established and established, the benefit of contemplation is the increase in knowledge and the acquisition of knowledge that is not attained, so thinking comes to knowledge, and remembering and thinking is a manifestation of intelligence, even if it is not united with it, and thinking is different from remembering, and acting is different from it as well. Almighty said: (Thus does Allah make clear to you [His] verses that you might give thought.) Thinking has two important characteristics: the integration and organization of past experiences with the discovery of modern responses, and the word thinking refers to many behavioral patterns, an example of the presence of thinking in the sense of Golan is the perceiving power of the sciences according to the eyes of the mind, the Almighty's saying: (Who remember Allāh while standing or sitting or [lying] on their sides and give thought to the creation of the heavens and the earth, [saying], "Our Lord, You did not create this aimlessly; exalted are You [above such a thing]; then protect us from the punishment of the Fire) The Qur'an directs and guides the mind to carry out the process of thinking about the creation of the heavens and the earth, in order to reach the knowledge of the Creator, Glory be to Him, and to sustain the universe, thus gaining the happiness of both worlds. Sahib Alzilal explained the relationship between the function of rational thinking and receiving revelation when interpreting the Almighty's verse: (Say, [O Muḥammad], "I do not tell you that I have the depositories [containing the provision] of Allāh or that I know the unseen, nor do I tell you that I am an angel. I only follow what is revealed to me." Say, "Is the blind equivalent to the seeing? Then will you not give thought?") Moreover, following the revelation alone is guidance and insight, and the one who is left without this guide is left blind. This is what this verse appreciates in clarity and strictness, so what is the matter of the human mind in this field?

The question and its answer in the Islamic conception is clear and simple. This mind, which God has endowed to man, is capable of receiving that revelation, and realizing its meanings, and this is his job, then this is his opportunity for light and guidance, and for discipline with this correct discipline that does not come to falsehood from before it or from behind it. But when this human mind is independent of itself, away from revelation, at that time, he is exposed to misguidance, deviation in vision, lack of vision, miscalculation and mismanagement. He is exposed to all of this because of the very nature of his composition in the vision of existence, parts, not wholes, experience after experience, incident after incident, and image after image... as it is difficult for him to see existence as a sentence that establishes judgments on the basis of this complete vision, and he puts on its basis a remarkable system of comprehensiveness and balance, and then remains when he is isolated from God's method and guidance, frequenting experiments, changing judgments, altering a system, perturbing between action and reactions, and faltering from the extreme right to the far left. And in all that he destroys human beings and decent human devices... and if he had followed the revelation, he would have done that on the sufficiency of mankind for all this evil, and made experiments and fluctuations in things, in the matter, in devices, and in machines... All of this is exposed after the nature of its composition, due to the desires, whims, and tendencies that have been entered into the human entity, which must have a regulator to ensure that it performs its functions in the continuation and advancement of human life, and do not exceed this safe limit, as it will lead to the destruction or relapse of life! And this discipline cannot be the human mind alone, for this mind must be disturbed under the pressure of different desires, and tendencies, by another discipline that is controlled by itself. And his eagerness after controlling it from defects as well, and this mind returns to him with every experience and every judgment in the field of human life; He does his experience and judgment, and to control his direction and movement.

And those who assign to the human mind a degree of authenticity in correctness, such as the degree of revelation, considering that both of them - the intellect and the revelation - are made by God, must be identical... These are based on reports about the value of reason that some human philosophers have said, but God Almighty did not say about them! Those who see that this mind suffices for revelation, even for a single human being, no matter how old his mind is, but what they say in this case is other than what God says... God has made his argument against people the revelation and the message, and he did not make this argument against their human intellect, not even their innate nature that God created them with from knowing and believing in their One Lord; God Almighty knows that the mind alone goes astray. And that instinct alone deviates, and that there is no protector for reason or the mind, unless the mind is the guide, the light and the insight. And those who claim that philosophy takes the place of religion, or that science - which is a product of the mind - suffices humanity from the guidance of God, they are saying something that has no basis in truth or reality as well... Since reality testifies that human life, whose systems are based on philosophical doctrines or on science, is the most miserable life in which a person suffers no matter how many doors are opened to him. And no matter how much production and income are doubled, and no matter how widely the causes and comforts of life are facilitated, it is not in return for life based on ignorance and spontaneity! Those who put the matter thus deny! Islam is a way of life that entrusts the human mind with guarantees that protect it from the defects of its own structure, and the defects of the pressures that fall upon it from desires, and tendencies. Then he establishes

the foundations for him and sets for him the rules that ensure his integrity in his launch of knowledge, knowledge and experience. It also ensures for him the integrity of the real life in which he lives according to the law of God, so that reality does not pressure him to deviate with his perceptions and methods as well!

Sahib Alzilal also explained the importance of thinking from the meaning of the noble Qur'anic verses, but this thinking is controlled by revelation and reason by accompanying God's revelation and His guidance is insightful, and by leaving God's revelation and his desire is blind. And the conjunction of a hadith about the Messenger ﷺ receiving revelation alone, with reference to blindness and sight, On the question that prompts thought.

The association of signs and their succession in this way in the context is a significant matter in the Qur'anic expression, as reflection is required and preserving it is a Qur'anic approach, rather, it is the controlled contemplation by the adjuster of revelation, with which he goes with him seeing in the light, not the absolute contemplation that is mired in darkness, blind, without evidence, no guidance, nor an illuminating book... And the human mind, when left within the framework of revelation, does not move in a narrow field, but rather moves in a very wide field... It moves in a field that is this whole existence, which contains the world of testimony and the world of the unseen as well, as well as the depths of the soul and the fields of events and all areas of life... Revelation the mind does not stop from anything except for the deviation of the method, poor vision, distortion of desires, and after that, it motivates him to move and be active, and this great tool that God gave to man - the mind - was only given to him to work and be active in guarding revelation and divine guidance.

As for Ibn Ashour, he explained the role of thinking in revealing the signs of God Almighty, and that it is a way to guide and the unification of God in His divinity. He said, reflecting on the Almighty's saying: (He causes the night to cover the day. Indeed, in that are signs for a people who give thought) And he made the mentioned things conditions for 'verses' that each of the mentioned matters includes many verses that are clear by correct consideration and thinking without illusions. Therefore, he applied the adjective thinking to the term "people" to indicate that repetitive, renewed thinking is a well-established characteristic of them, so that it made one of the components of their nationalism. That is, you made them, as we explained in the meaning of the word "people" for that when God Almighty says: (are signs for a people who use reason.) This indicates that those who ascribe themselves to thinking from among the naturalists, they justified the origins of beings from matter and denied the chosen subject, they thought nothing but short thinking mixed with illusions, not what is required by the intellect, when the ill and the newborns suspected them of the origin of creation. In thinking, the form denoting affection was used, and the present tense was used to indicate intense and repetitive thinking. Ibn Ashour said when explaining the Almighty's verse: (He causes to grow for you thereby the crops, olives, palm trees, grapevines, and of all the fruits. Indeed, in that is a sign for a people who give thought.) This proof is one of the evidences of great divine power, and the purpose of it is inference mixed with remembrance with grace. And the insertion of the term "people" to indicate that contemplation is one of their traits, and the connotation of this is assigned to describing contemplation because it is a hidden sign of its gradual occurrence. It is an exposition of the polytheists who were not guided, including an indication of God's uniqueness in divinity, because they are a people who do not think.

The second requirement: Remembrance of God Almighty:

It was mentioned in the Holy Qur'an in three hundred and twenty places: the remembrance is taken from the dhikr, and the sources mention the faces and analogies of the dhikr in twenty faces, and what concerns us is the dhikr with the tongue and the heart, and the heart. And what Al-Ragheb Al-Isfahani and Al-Thamin Al-Halabi held is that the remembrance is originally a reminder of the heart and the tongue, or both, from forgetting or from perpetuating memorization, and on these types are all the verses and all the other meanings mentioned, which are no more than means of remembrance, such as monotheism, faith and prayer, and some of these aspects have been included in the dhikr and what are its components, rather, it is one of his means, and some of them are from what is required by remembrance, such as informing and admonishing, and among the examples of his coming in the place of urging contemplation of the universe is the Almighty's saying: (And it is He who has made the night and the day in succession for whoever desires to remember or desires gratitude.) Remembrance have been associated in the Qur'an with people of understanding in many instances, because people of understanding are the ones who do remembrance. (And none will remember except those of understanding.)

Dr. Abbas Mahjoub said, "Those who take the scientific method as the basis for their thinking are the ones who have understanding, because it is this method that leads to the remembrance of God and piety." In that, God Almighty says: (Indeed in that is a reminder for those of understanding.)

Sahib Alzilal said when interpreting the Almighty's verse: (And this is the path of your Lord, [leading] straight. We have detailed the verses for a people who remember. (127) For them will be the Home of Peace [i.e., Paradise] with their Lord. And He will be their protecting friend because of what they used to do.) This is the path... the path of your Lord... with this reassuring addition that inspires confidence and heralds the end...

This is his Sunnah of guidance and misguidance, and this is his law of lawfulness and sanctity, both are equal in the scale of God and both are together in the context of the Qur'an. God has explained His verses and clarified them, but those who remember and do not forget or neglect are the ones who benefit from this explanation and this detail, so the believing heart is a heart that remembers and does not forget. Those who remember for them the abode of peace with their Lord is the abode of tranquility and security. It is guaranteed with their Lord that it will not be lost, and He is their guardian, their helper, their shepherd, and their guarantor. That is what they used to do, so it is the reward for success in affliction.

Ibn Ashour said: "Remembrance is contemplation, and it is in this form that it is only applied to the mind's mention of its intelligibles, that is, its movement in its information, so it is close to contemplation, however, the remembrance of what was derived from the dhikr substance, which is originally the flow of the word on the tongue, and by which it also expresses the danger of the known in the mind after its forgetfulness and absence from it, was felt as the movement of the mind in information established in it before. That is why I prefer here without "May you reflect" to indicate that the inference on the oneness of God Almighty has been established in the souls by nature, and with the invitation and evidence presented to them, so it is sufficient for the inference merely to notify these evidence in the mind. And Ibn Ashour indicated that remembrance involves more care and a need for remembrance when interpreting the Almighty's verse: (Say, [O Muḥammad], "To whom belongs the earth and whoever is in it, if you should know?"- (85) They will say, "To Allāh." Say, "Then will you not remember?) And the sentence "Say, do you not remember" occurred in response to their affirmation and recognition that it is for God, and the question is a denial of their lack of remembrance of that. That is, their minds understand the evidence of this that the Almighty is alone in the divine, and he is singled out by remembrance of what is in some of it of hidden significance and the need for consideration. And Al-Zamakhshari said in its interpretation: "Do you not remember, then learn that whoever created the earth and those in it were an invention, he was able to re-create, and it was true that some of his creation should not be associated with him in the Lordship"

The third requirement: Contemplation:

It has been mentioned in the Holy Qur'an with the meaning of thinking four times, Almighty said: (And those who arrange [each] matter) It means angels entrusted with managing matters Thinking about it, looking at what its outcome will be, almighty said: (Do they not consider the Qur'an (with care)? Had it been from other Than Allah, they would surely have found therein Much discrepancy.) Almighty said: (Is it then that they do not ponder over what is said, or is it that there has come to them that which did not come to their fathers of old?) and Almighty said: ([This is] a blessed Book which We have revealed to you, [O Muḥammad], that they might reflect upon its verses and that those of understanding would be reminded.) It is noted in the verses in which reflection is mentioned that the matter is always associated with reflecting on the verses of the Noble Qur'an, and this is an indication that the implementation of thought in the Qur'an requires a special process of thinking, so reflection in the Qur'an is not called reflection unless it leads to the realization of thought or action. Sahib Alzilah said when interpreting the Almighty's verse: (Then have they not reflected over the word [i.e., the Qur'ān], or has there come to them that which had not come to their forefathers?-(69) Or did they not know their Messenger, so they are toward him disacknowledging?(70) Or do they say, "In him is madness"? Rather, he brought them the truth, but most of them, to the truth, are averse.(71) But if the Truth [i.e., Allāh] had followed their inclinations, the heavens and the earth and whoever is in them would have been ruined. Rather, We have brought them their message,[965] but they, from their message, are turning away.(72) Or do you, [O Muḥammad], ask them for payment? But the reward of your Lord is best, and He is the best of providers.(73) And indeed, you invite them to a straight path.(74) But indeed, those who do not believe in the Hereafter are deviating from the path.)

He moves them from the scene of reprimand in the afterlife, and brings them back to the world again! He returns to them to ask and marvel at their strange position...What prevents them from believing in what their faithful messenger brought them? What are the suspicions that weave in their chests and work to prevent them from guidance? What is their excuse for rejecting it? And Samar in their councils Grocery bad in it? And it is the pure truth and the straight path: the likeness of what Muhammad, the Messenger of God, peace and blessings be upon him, came, does not have the power to contemplate it to remain aloof from it, it contains beauty, it contains perfection, it contains harmony, it contains attractiveness, it contains fit of nature, it contains emotional revelations, it contains nourishment for the heart, it contains the increase of thought, it contains greatness of attitudes, it contains correct methods, and it contains firm legislation. ...And it contains everything that energizes all the elements of instinct, nourishes and satisfies it: "Do they not manage to say?" if? This is the secret of their turning away from him, because they did not contemplate it. As for Ibn Ashour, he said in its interpretation: "These interrogations are used in error in the manner of the transmitted metaphor, because the clarity of the error necessitates doubt that it came from the wise and that doubt necessitates the question of its occurrence from reasonable people. And the fate of the meanings of these interrogations is that it is a census of their misguidance and error, so they are singled out by mentioning such matters, as well as protesting against them

and cutting their excuse and awakening to them that all the characteristics of the Messenger are indicative of his sincerity. The first question is about their failure to reflect upon what is recited to them of the Qur'an, which is what is meant by saying, i.e. speech. God Almighty said, pondering: Implementation of rational consideration in the indications of the evidence for what they have been erected, and its origin is that of looking into the matter, i.e. what does not appear from them to the contemplator to begin with. When the Almighty says: (Do they not then consider the Qur'an carefully? Had it been from other than Allāh, they would surely have found therein many a contradiction.) The meaning is that if they reflect on the words of the Qur'an, they would know that the truth is in the evidence of its miraculousness and the validity of its purposes. Their persistence and stubbornness were only because they did not reflect upon the saying, and this is one of the causes that overwhelmed them in disbelief.

The fourth requirement: deepening:

It is the knowledge and understanding of a thing, and its derivation from Shaqq and Al-Fath. The owner of the tongue said: Jurisprudence is the knowledge of something and understanding it, and it has prevailed over the knowledge of religion because of its sovereignty, honor and virtue over all other types of knowledge. Ibn al-Atheer said: Its derivation is from al-Fath and al-Fath, and it was said: It is the attainment of an absent knowledge with a witnessing knowledge, which is more special than knowledge. And it was said: It is the jurisprudence of hidden things, so it is more special than the absolute understanding. Examples of its occurrence in the Noble Qur'an in the field of urging the understanding of the human soul are the Almighty's saying: (And it is He who produced you from one soul and [gave you] a place of dwelling and of storage.[331] We have detailed the signs for a people who understand.)

Sahib Alzilalsaid in its interpretation: "It is the direct touch this time... the touch in the same human soul, the one human soul united in being and truth in the male and female, in which life begins its first step of reproduction with the fertilized cell, so the soul is the repository of this cell in the man's core, and the soul is its stable in the womb of the female... Then life begins to grow and spread, so if races and colours, if things and languages, and if peoples and tribes, and if patterns are countless, and patterns that continue to vary as long as life, "We have detailed the verses for a people who understand"... So jurisprudence here is necessary to comprehend God's creation in this one soul, from which patterns and patterns emerge. And in order to realize the wondrous consents behind the adoption of cross-pollination to multiply and to always provide the appropriate numbers of males and females in the human world, to take place the process of mating, which God destined to be a means of fertilization and multiplication, and a means of bringing up children in conditions that preserve their humanity and make them capable of human life.

And Ibn Ashour said: "And his saying, "We have detailed the verses for a people who understand" is a shortening of its previous counterpart, intended to remind and excuse, and changed from "know" to "understand." Because the sign of their establishment on these phases of stability and deposition and the wisdom in them is a precise indication that needs to be contemplated, because the addressees were reluctant to do so, so he expressed their knowledge that it is jurisprudence, contrary to the indication of the stars on the wisdom of being guided by it, it is a frequent indication and an exposition that the polytheists neither know nor understand, for knowledge and knowledge agree with the truth.

The fifth requirement: Understanding:

Understanding is a human body by which the meanings of what is good are realized, Almighty said: (We made Solomon understand it. Each We gave discretion and knowledge, and We let the mountains and the birds hymn [Our praises] with David. We were Active [in this].) And that is either because God has given him from the virtue of the power of understanding what he has realized, or that He has revealed to him and singled him out for it, the Qur'an has praised Solomon in the field of his understanding of ruling between people with justice and truth, and it is required of every human being to strive hard to understand the Book of God and the reality of his existence in the universe.

The sixth requirement: Consider:

Looking is turning the eye around and moving it over things, al-Fayrouz Abadi said: "Looking is the turning of insight to perceive and see a thing. It may mean contemplation and examination, and it may mean knowledge obtained after examination. The Qur'an urges people to consider many verses, Almighty said: (Then do they not look at the camels - how they are created?) and Almighty said: (Do they not look into the realm of the heavens and the earth and everything that Allāh has created and [think] that perhaps their appointed time has come near? So in what statement [i.e., message] hereafter will they believe?) Ibn Ashour said in its interpretation: "The appeal stems from his saying, "And if your Lord had willed, those on earth would have believed, all of them together. So do you hate people...etc." He divided people into two categories: Believers and unbelievers, that is, invite them to look at the evidence of oneness and guide them to the attainment of the causes of faith and to ward off the delusions of unbelief, and that is by guiding the consideration and inference of what is around the human being from the conditions of the existents and their dispositions that indicate oneness, such as the bodies of the planets and the ordinances of their paths, and the conditions of light and darkness, winds, clouds and rain, as well as seas and mountains. The sentence opened with "Say" to pay

attention to its content, and it generalized what is in the heavens and the earth so that every soul would turn to what is closer to it and easier to infer with it. And looking: here it is used for what is suitable for heart sight and visual consideration, therefore, he deviated from his implementation of one of the two actions, so that he would not be tempted by him. Then came after him the suspended question for both verbs, so that it became a burden to look at both of them alike, and it became valid for the real and figurative meanings, and this is one of the purposes of the Qur'an.

Sayyid Qutb explains the reason for turning away from meditation that affects the infidels, saying: With these clear verses, the servants are in heedlessness, their eyes are not directed, their hearts are not awakened, and they do not cease from their mockery and denial, and their haste with the torment that the messengers warn them with. The Almighty said: (But when it is said to them, "Beware of what is before you and what is behind you; [1271] perhaps you will receive mercy... (46) And no sign comes to them from the signs of their Lord except that they are from it turning away. (47) And when it is said to them, "Spend from that which Allāh has provided for you," those who disbelieve say to those who believe, "Should we feed one whom, if Allāh had willed, He would have fed? You are not but in clear error." (48) And they say, "When is this promise, if you should be truthful?"

Those verses by themselves do not provoke in their hearts aspiration, contemplation, sensitivity and piety, and by themselves they are sufficient to provoke in the open heart a tremor, tremor and uprising, and you confuse it with existence, this open book indicates that each of its pages refers to the greatness of the Creator and the gentleness of his management and appreciation, but these obscured people do not see it, and if they see it, they do not contemplate it, and God is great in His mercy. He does not leave them with this without a messenger who warns them, directs them, and calls them to the Lord of this universe and the Creator of this existence, it arouses in their hearts sensitivity, fear and piety, and warns them of the causes of anger and torment, which surround them from before them and from behind them. Do they not pay attention to it and fall into it at every step of their steps, and verses follow them in addition to the cosmic verses that surround them wherever they go, but despite this they remain silent about their blindness, the Almighty said: (But when it is said to them, "Beware of what is before you and what is behind you; [1271] perhaps you will receive mercy... (46) And no sign comes to them from the signs of their Lord except that they are from it turning away.)

The Noble Qur'an drew the attention of the servants to the integrity of the universe system and meditation on the creation of man and the verses about that are many, they lead man to be fascinated by the making of the Mighty, rather the Muslim is commanded to contemplate God's perfect work." God Almighty says: (And you will see the mountains and think them solid, but they shall pass away as the passing away of the clouds. The Work of Allah, who perfected all things, verily! He is Well-Acquainted with what you do.)

Research results

1. The Holy Qur'an focused on the mind as one of the basic means of knowledge, and it is the center of thinking, perception, mouth, contemplation, awareness and feeling, it has the ability to retrieve, use and invest information, and this ability is capable of growth and development if the correct scientific method is used to develop these capabilities.
2. To highlight the integrative relationship between the task of the mind and its synonyms in discovering, clarifying and using knowledge and directing sensory perception in the paths that the mind deems closer to the truth, more useful and feasible in reaching it.
3. Highlighting the functions performed by the mind as a way to guidance, truth and guidance on the one hand, and on the other hand, a way to reveal the signs of God in souls and horizons.

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